

Technical Note

Shedding Light on Vehicular Communication: A Review of the Latest Vehicular Visible Light Communication Channel Models - Materials & Methods

G.M. Dotreppe, A. Mentens, J. Coosemans, P. Van den Bossche, V.A. Jacobs

Abstract—In order to examine current channel modelling approaches for V-VLC within the framework of Intelligent Transportation Systems, a review of the literature within the period between 2013 and 2024 is performed. This assesses the advancements of V-VLC as a valuable addition to vehicular networks, with a specific emphasis on photometric aspects of the optical channel models. To provide a traceable and reproducible literature study, this work employs a systematic approach. The search terms, databases and inclusion/exclusion criteria are presented for the interested readers.

Index Terms—V-VLC, Channel Modelling, Luminous Intensity Distribution, V2V, ITS

I. INTRODUCTION

THE survey caters to both novices and seasoned researchers in the field of V-VLC, offering insights into physical channel models and fostering a comprehensive understanding of recent advancements. For the interested reader, the complete literature retrieval methodology is presented in this short technical note. The purpose is to allow all to reproduce the literature search in an efficient and traceable way. By providing readers with typical search terms found in the field of V-VLC, a search string can be created applicable to various data bases.

Similarly to Yahia et al. [1] and Shaaban et al. [2], a systematic approach for reference retrieval is followed. Accordingly, the search terms, databases, and criteria for inclusion and exclusion utilised in the two-stage selection process are presented to ensure reproducibility. Section II presents the complete literature retrieval process. In section III, an overview of the used literature in the survey is presented in a summarised form. This can be used for inter comparison of the various publications, as well as to understand which characteristics have been analysed.

For the ease of reading, all tables and acronyms are presented at the end of this document, after the bibliography.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This paper relies on two types of sources: review articles and journal papers. Review articles are used to synthesise

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Manuscript received

existing research and examine the development of the presented ideas, while journal papers showcase the most recent advancements in V-VLC channel modelling. The bibliographic databases utilised include *Web of Science*, *IEEE*, *Scopus*, and *Springer*. Springer's database shows less advanced search features compared to others, resulting in significantly less or no results. Review articles were retrieved based on specific keywords related to the field of study, as outlined in Table I. The publication time frame was limited to 2013-2024 in order to encompass research from the past decade. Springer was not used in this part due to the lack of specific filters for retrieving review papers. In total 35 review articles were identified. 17 duplicates were excluded through the use of *Rayyan.io*. From the 20 selected papers, 18 were retrieved. After a first screening stage based on title and abstract solely, 14 papers were retained. The full read carried out by the first author only resulted in 11 retained papers based on predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria as per Table II.

Based on recurring keywords and information from the retrieved review papers, a database of original research papers is created to summarise, critically analyse, and consolidate the latest advancements. The keywords used to search for papers in the same databases as the review papers are given in Table III. To only encompass the latest research advancements, the time frame for sourcing original research papers is confined to the years 2021 through 2024. Furthermore, this study will limit itself to peer reviewed journal publications only.

In total, 119 papers have been found. Through *Rayyan.ai* duplicates are removed resulting in 90 unique papers for the two screening rounds. Following the inclusion and exclusion criteria outlined in Table IV, 46 papers are retained based on the title and abstract. The screening phases were performed by 3 authors of this paper. Disagreements were deliberated upon until a mutual consensus was achieved, with a preference for providing the benefit of doubt in cases of uncertainty. Consequently, it was deemed preferable to include a paper at this juncture to facilitate a final decision subsequent to a thorough examination of the full text. Following the full read, conducted exclusively by the first author of this paper during the second screening stage, a total of 30 papers were retained for subsequent discussion and analysis. The other papers are rejected because they are out of scope of this review, not within the inclusion criteria or belonging to the exclusion criteria. A flow diagram of the complete review procedure is

Figure 1. Prism flow chart of the paper retrieval and selection procedure. Wrong population refers to VLC research on aerial and underwater vehicles, as well as intra-vehicular communication, indoor communication and visible light positioning amongst others. Wrong topic relates to the fact that the paper is focused on aspects other than the channel modelling for a V-VLC system. Finally, the wrong document type refers to the case where a review paper or conference proceeding was found when looking for original research papers or vice versa.

given in Fig. 1.

Finally, a screening of the existing standardization efforts is performed to assess the readiness of the technology to be implemented in a broad vehicular environment. Several national and international standardization organisms such as NBN (“Bureau voor Normalisatie/Bureau de Normalisation”, the Belgian national standards body), IEEE (Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers) and ISO (International Organization for standardization) are consulted. The standardization efforts focusing on the integration of VLC into a vehicular environment are limited to a few technical notes. These documents are discussed in section III-C.

III. RESULTS

This section presents a brief overview of the employed references and their respective characteristics.

A. Existing reviews

Table V presents an overview of the included review papers and their main focus.

B. Latest V-VLC Channel Models

Table VI lists all the characteristic features of the retained research papers. Table VII focusses specifically on ML methods.

C. Standardization Efforts

The main standardization efforts regarding VLC/OWC are carried out by IEEE and ISO. A brief overview of the different relevant standards is given in Table VIII.

IV. CONCLUSION

The literature from the past decade is systematically analysed, covering general modelling approaches, light source modelling methodologies, and influencing factors. Through the presented method, every reader should be capable to reproduce the literature retrieval process, allowing for a straightforward update of the literature in due time.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We acknowledge Flanders’ Make for the support to our research centre.

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TABLES

Table I
KEYWORDS AND SYNONYMS USED TO BUILD A SEARCH STRING
EMPLOYED IN THE RETRIEVAL OF REVIEW PAPERS.

Boolean	Keyword	Boolean	Synonyms
AND	Vehicular	OR	Vehicle
		OR	Car
		OR	Automotive
		OR	Automobile
		OR	Outdoor
		OR	Transportation
		OR	Transport
		OR	Intelligent Transportation System
		OR	Intelligent Transport System
		OR	ITS
AND	Visible Light Communication	OR	Light Communication
		OR	VLC
		OR	Optical Communication
		OR	Optical Wireless Communication
		OR	OWC
		OR	Optical Camera Communication
		OR	OCC
AND	Review	OR	Survey
		OR	Overview

Table II
INCLUSION AND EXCLUSION CRITERIA EMPLOYED FOR THE RETRIEVED
REVIEW PAPERS.

Inclusion Criteria
Review papers on the subject of V-VLC channel modelling
Publication Date between 2013 and 2024
Publications containing each keyword or their respective synonym in the title, abstract or keywords and metadata
Publications related to the research questions
Exclusion Criteria
Review papers on the general subject of VLC
Review papers not related to the vehicular environment (or associated synonyms)
Papers from which full versions are not available
Papers in a language different from English, French or Dutch
Non review papers
Non peer-reviewed papers

Table III
KEYWORDS AND SYNONYMS USED TO BUILD A SEARCH STRING
EMPLOYED IN THE RETRIEVAL OF PEER REVIEWED JOURNAL PAPERS.

Boolean	Keyword	Boolean	Synonyms
AND	Vehicular	OR	Vehicle
		OR	Car
		OR	Automotive
		OR	Automobile
		OR	Outdoor
		OR	Transportation
		OR	Transport
		OR	Intelligent Transportation System
		OR	Intelligent Transport System ITS
AND	Visible Light Communication	OR	Light Communication
		OR	VLC
		OR	Optical Communication
		OR	Optical Wireless Communication
		OR	OWC
		OR	Optical Camera Communication
		OR	OCC
		OR	Light-Fidelity
		OR	Li-Fi
AND	Channel Model	OR	Channel Characteristics
		OR	Channel
		OR	Optical Model
		OR	Path Loss
		OR	Channel Link
		OR	Channel Simulation
AND	Vehicle to Vehicle	OR	Car to Car
		OR	V2V
		OR	C2C
AND	Luminous Intensity Distribution	OR	Radiation Pattern
		OR	Irradiance Pattern
		OR	Light Propagation
AND	LED	OR	Matrix LED
		OR	Beam
		OR	Headlamp
		OR	Taillight

Table IV
INCLUSION AND EXCLUSION CRITERIA EMPLOYED FOR THE RETRIEVED
RESEARCH PAPERS.

Inclusion Criteria
Papers focusing on the subject of V-VLC channel modelling Papers focusing on the transmitter Papers focusing on the vehicular environment Papers published between 2021 and 2024 Papers containing each keyword or their respective synonym in the title, abstract or keywords and metadata Papers related to the research questions Papers published in a peer reviewed journal
Exclusion Criteria
Publications not focusing on the channel modelling Review papers Papers focusing solely on receivers Papers focusing on aerial or underwater communication Papers focusing on indoor communication Papers focusing on the reflections aspects Papers from which full versions are not available Papers in a language different from English, French or Dutch Conference proceedings Non peer-reviewed papers Papers submitted prior to 2021

Table V
SUMMARY OF THE RELEVANT SURVEYS AND REVIEWS INCLUDED FOR THE PRELIMINARIES.

Reference	Year	Focus
Marè et al. [3]	2016	Exploration of V-VLC as an alternative/additional communication medium for ITS. This highlights the early stage shortcomings, some still relevant today.
Cailean & Dimian [4]	2017	First survey on the usage of VLC in a vehicular environment with a focus on the mitigation of influencing factors, mainly the noise from parasitic light sources.
Ndjiongue & Ferreira [5]	2018	Reviews the use of VLC in outdoor environments considering influencing factors such as parasitic light, adverse weather conditions, receiver design and modulation techniques. An outdoor VLC system is presented, showing the influence of an optical filter on the channel.
Shaaban & Faruque [6]	2020	Investigation on the V-VLC physical layer security and development of a channel model and security protocol for enhanced secrecy performance.
Mei et al. [7]	2020	Overview on the use of OWC for unmanned autonomous vehicles, including aerial, ground and water based vehicles. The primary focus is on examining the impact of different environments on communication and exploring the strategies proposed in current research to mitigate their adverse effects.
Shaaban et al. [2]	2021	Systematic approach to present the current state of VLC systems targeted at a vehicular environment. Mainly a comparison of the LD- and LED-based systems is provided.
Memedi & Dresler [8]	2021	Complete overview of the current challenges and future research paths related to the field of vehicular VLC.
Yahia et al. [1]	2021	Systematic review study on the various channel modelling techniques used for VLC, encompassing both in- and outdoor applications.
Hasan et al. [9]	2022	Reviews the OCC systems in a vehicular environment considering modulation schemes, channel properties, research trends, technical challenges and standardisation efforts.
Sefako et al. [10]	2024	Survey on the existing ML based channel models applicable to ITS.
Al Hasnawi & Margh- escu [11]	2024	Comprehensive review of V-VLC including its architecture, several influencing factors, applications and future research trends.
This survey		This work provides an in-depth overview of VLC channel models tailored for vehicular environments, emphasising the modelling approaches, light source characteristics, and key influencing factors. All models are analysed with a special attention to the photometry governing the spatial distribution of the optical radiation.

Table VI

SUMMARY OF THE MODELLING APPROACHES USED IN RECENT LITERATURE. ALL ABRIVIATIONS CAN BE FOUND IN THE LIST OF ACRONYMS AT THE END OF THIS DOCUMENT.

Reference	Year	Modelling Approach	Emission Pattern	Light Source	Channel Characteristics	Influencing Factors
Eldeeb et al. [12]	2021	RT	Measured	TL	PL, RMS Delay Spread	RR, VR
Eldeeb et al. [13]	2021	RT	Measured	HL & TL	PL, P_R	GG, VR, PLS
Turan & Coleri [14]	2021	ML	Measured	HL	PL, CFR	IVD, GG, RC, AT, PLS
Alsalamy et al. [15]	2021	Analytical, MC	GL, Gaussian, Measured	HL	PL, CIR	IVD, GG, RC, VS
Alsalamy et al. [16]	2021	Analytical, MC	GL	HL	PL, CIR	IVD, VR, RC
Singh et al. [17]	2021	Analytical	Measured	HL	BER, SINR	IVD, VR, RC, AT, PLS, Lambertian Order (FWHM)
Amjad et al. [18]	2021	Measured	Measured	HL	RSS	IVD, PLS
Turan et al. [19]	2022	Measured	Fitted	HL	PL, CIR, BER	IVD, VR
Meucci et al. [20]	2022	Measured	Measured, Fitted	HL & TL	SNR, PER	IVD, GG
Yahia et al. [21]	2022	RT	Measured	HL	RSS, BER	GG, AT, PLS
Alsalamy et al. [22]	2022	Analytical	Measured, Fitted	HL	BER, SNR	IVD, VR, RC, AT
Sharda et al. [23]	2022	Analytical, MC	Measured	TL	BER, Outage Probability, Diversity order	IVD, GG, AT
Li et al. [24]	2022	Analytical, Measured	GL, Measured	HL	BER, SNR, Achievable Data Rate	GG, AT, LED Current
Mishra et al. [25]	2022	Analytical	GL	HL	CIR, BER, SNR	IVD, GG, Modulation Scheme
Sharda et al. [26]	2022	Analytical MC	Measured	HL	PL, DMT	IVD, VR, AT, Shadowing Probability
Liu et al. [27]	2023	Analytical	GL	HL	SNR	IVD, RC, VS
Aly et al. [28]	2023	Measured	Measured	HL	BER, SNR	GG, RC, VS, PD Mounting Height
Refas et al. [29]	2023	RT	Measured	HL & TL	BER	Bandwidth, P_s , Relay Number
Ullah et al. [30]	2023	ML	Measured	HL	PL	IVD, GG, Relative VS
Eldeeb et al. [31]	2023	RT	Measured	HL	Energy Efficiency, Spectral Efficiency	GG, Location and Amount of IRS, AT, PLS
Gurbilek et al. [32]	2023	Blind Estimation, Measured	N/A	HL	CFR, Spectral Efficiency	IVD, GG, PLS
Plattner & Ostermayer [33]	2023	Measured	N/A	TL	BER, PER	IVD, GG, AT, Pulse Width Ratio
Yahia et al. [34]	2023	RT	Not Specified	HL	PER	IVD, GG
Alsalamy et al. [35]	2023	Analytical	Measured, Fitted	HL	PL, SNR, Channel Capacity	IVD, RC, AT
El-Mokadem et al. [?]	2023	Analytical	Not Specified	HL & TL	BER, Q-factor, P_S	GG, AT, Aperture size, FWHM, Quantum Efficiency, Receiver Responsivity
Rabiepoor et al. [36]	2024	Analytical	GL, Gaussian, Fitted	HL	PL, BER	IVD, GG, Number and Location of IRS
Plattner et al. [37]	2024	Measured	N/A	TL	BER	AT
Al-Sallami et al. [?]	2024	Analytical, Measured	GL, Gaussian, Measured, N/A	HL	Capacity Bounds	IVD, AT, RC
Sharda [38]	2024	Analytical, RT	Fitted	HL	PL, Energy Efficiency	IVD, AT, VR
Raissouni et al. [39]	2024	Analytical	GL	HL	PL, Channel DC-gain, RMS Delay Spread	IVD, GG, RR, Lambertian Order (FWHM), Focal length
Yang et al. [40]	2024	Analytical	Gaussian	HL	PL, SNR, Channel Capacity, Outage Probability	IVD, GG, AT, RR, Mountain side reflections

Table VII
COMPARISON OF MACHINE LEARNING TECHNIQUES USED IN VLC.

	CM/SP	Environment	Purpose	ML Technique
[41]	SP	Indoor	Link outage prediction.	DL-LSTM
[42]	SP	Indoor	Handover optimisation in multi-user environments.	DL-LSTM for link outage prediction & Q-learn for handover decision.
[43]	SP/CM	Indoor	Limiting low frequency noise influence on E2E systems.	IBCM
[44]	SP	Indoor	Decoding scheme improvements for MIMO systems.	CNN
[45]	CM	Indoor/Outdoor	Accurate deterministic and random noise modelling for E2E based systems.	CNJCE
[46]	CM	Indoor/Outdoor	Inclusion of deterministic and random noise to a channel estimator for E2E AE comparison.	ACNJCE
[47]	CM	Indoor	Propose a differentiable channel model for E2E OFDM based VLC system design.	BiLSTM, BiGRU & Transformer
[48]	SP	Indoor	Optimisation of user selection, transmission power and channel estimation in hybrid RF-VLC systems.	Vertical FL for user selection and transmission power optimisation. MLP for channel estimation.
[49]	CM	Underwater	Create a channel estimator for underwater VLC.	Ensemble Learning
[50]	SP	Vehicular	Removing sunlight noise.	KNN
[51]	SP	Vehicular	Limitation of motion blur and ambient light noise on OCC systems.	YOLO for real-time multiple light source tracking. NN decoder and AI-based error correction for data decoding.
[14]	CM	Vehicular	PL and CFR prediction under dynamic road conditions.	MLP RBF for PL and CFR. RaFo for PL.
[30]	CM	Vehicular	Jamming detection and PL estimation in a heterogeneous RF-VLC communication system.	Hybrid MLP, BiLSTM and GRU for jamming detection. Hybrid MLP and Bagged Tree Ensemble Learning for PL estimation.

CM = Channel Modelling, SP = Signal Processing.

Table VIII
SUMMARY OF THE CURRENT STANDARDISATION EFFORTS RELATED TO VEHICULAR AND OPTICAL COMMUNICATION.

Standard	Year	Focus	Key Features
ISO 21218:2018 [52]	2018	C-ITS	Builds upon ISO 21217:2014. Supports hybrid communication technologies for ITS. Focuses on the access layer and common functionalities. No specifications regarding the communication technology.
IEEE 802.15.7 [53]	2018	OWC	Specifies modulation, coding, and frame structures for optical wireless communication. Defines six PHY layers for various applications. Supports dimming and flicker mitigation. Not specific to automotive applications.
ISO 21217:2020 [54]	2020	C-ITS	Defines reference architecture for ITS stations and communication based on OSI model. Updates include security, hybrid communications, and alignment with other standards. No specifications regarding the communication technology.
ISO/NP 22738:2020 [55]	2020	OCC	Standardizing Optical Camera Communication (OCC) within ITS. Requires IEEE 802.15.7 PHY IV for OCC. Supports modulation schemes like S2-PSK and HS-PSK. Dimming and flicker mitigation are mandatory.
IEEE 802.15.13 [56]	2023	OWC	Targets high data rate (up to 2.192 Gb/s), large range (up to 200m) OWC systems. Defines two PHY layers (PM-PHY, HB-PHY). Supports MIMO and mobile applications.
IEEE 802.11bb [57]	2023	LC	Provides amendments to IEEE 802.11 for light communication (LC). Supports uplink/downlink with minimum 10 Mb/s. Uses near-infrared light (800-1000 nm), limiting dual use for illumination and communication.

Table IX
LIST OF ACRONYMS.

Abbreviation	Definition	Abbreviation	Definition
2D-DBSCAN	2D Density Based Spatial Clustering Applications	3D-DBSCAN	3D Density Based Spatial Clustering Applications
ACNJCE	Attention-based Comprehensive Noise Joint Channel Estimator	ADAS	Advanced Driver Aid System
AE	Autoencoder	AFS	Adaptive Front-Lighting Systems
ANN	Artificial Neural Network	APP	Application Layer
AT	Atmospheric Turbulence	AV	Autonomous Vehicles
AWGN	Additive White Gaussian Noise	BER	Bit Error Rate
BiGRU	Bidirectional Gated Recurrent Unit	BiLSTM	Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory
BSDF	Bidirectional Scattering Distribution Function	C2C	Car-to-Car
C-ITS	Cooperative Intelligent Transportation Systems	C-V2X	Cellular Vehicle to Everything
CAD	Computer Aided Design	CFR	Channel Frequency Response
CIR	Channel Impulse Response	CM	Channel Modelling
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network	CNJCE	Comprehensive Noise Joint Channel Estimator
COTS	Commercial Off-The-Shelf	CSK	Colour Shift Keying
DC	Direct Current	DCNN	Deep Convolutional Neural Network
DL	Deep Learning	DMT	Diversity Multiplexing Trade-off
DNN	Deep Neural Network	DRL	Daytime Running Lights
DSRC	Dedicated Short Range Communication	DSSS	Direct Sequence Spread Spectrum
E2E	End-to-End	ECU	Electronic Control Unit
EM	Electromagnetic	EV	Electric Vehicle
FL	Federated Learning	FOV	Field-of-View
FSO	Free-Space Optical communication	FWHM	Full Width at Half Maximum
GBM	Geometric Based Models	GBSM	Geometric Based Stochastic Models
GBDM	Geometric Based Deterministic Models	GG	General Geometry
GL	Generalised Lambertian	GRU	Gated Recurrent Unit
HB-PHY	High Bandwidth PHY	HL	Headlight
HS-PSK	Hybrid Spatial Phase Shift Keying	IBCM	In-Band Channel Model
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies	IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers	ILMD	Imaging Luminance Measurement Device
IM	Intensity Modulation	IoT	Internet-of-Things
IR	Infra-Red	IRS	Intelligent Reflecting Surface
ISO	International Organization for Standardization	ITS	Intelligent Transportation Systems
IVD	Inter-Vehicular Distance	KNN	K-Nearest Neighbor
LC	Light Communication	LD	Laser Diode
LED	Light Emitting Diode	Li-Fi	Light-Fidelity
LID	Luminous Intensity Distribution	LOS	Line-of-Sight
LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory	MAC	Medium Access Control
MAE	Mean Absolute Error	MIMO	Multiple-Input Multiple-Output
ML	Machine Learning	MLP	Multilayer Perceptron
NBN	Belgian National Standards Body	NLOS	Non-Line-of-Sight
NN	Neural Network	NRZ	Non-Return-to-Zero
OCC	Optical Camera Communication	OFDM	Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing
OLED	Organic Light Emitting Diode	OOK	On-Off Keying
OWC	Optical Wireless Communication	PAM	Pulse Amplitude Modulation
PBL	Probability Bayesian Learning	PD	Photodiode
PDF	Power Density Function	PDR	Packet Delivery Ratio
PER	Packet Error Rate	PHY	Physical Layer
PL	Path Losses	PLS	Parasitic Light Sources
PM-PHY	Pulse Modulation PHY	QAM	Quadrature Amplitude Modulation
RaFo	Random Forest	RBF	Radial Basis Function
RC	Road Conditions	RF	Radio Frequency
RID	Radiant Intensity Distribution	RMS	Root Mean Square
RNN	Recurrent Neural Network	RR	Road Reflections
RSS	Received Signal Strength	RT	Ray Tracing
Rx	Receiver	S2-PSK	Spatial 2 Phase Shift Keying
SDMA	Space Division Multiple Access	SDR	Software Defined Radio
SINR	Signal-to-Interference-Noise Ratio	SISO	Single-Input Single-Output
SNR	Signal to Noise Ratio	SP	Signal Processing
SPAD	Single Photon Avalanche Diode	SSL	Solid State Light
TC	Technical Committee	TDA	Time Domain Averaging
TG	Task Group	TL	Taillight
Tx	Transmitter	V2I	Vehicle-to-Infrastructure
V2V	Vehicle-to-Vehicle	V2X	Vehicle-to-Everything
VLC	Visible Light Communication	VPPM	Variable Pulse-Position Modulation
VR	Vehicle Reflections	V-RF	Vehicular-RF Communication
V-VLC	Vehicular Visible Light Communication	VS	Vehicle Speed
WDM	Wave Division Multiplexing	WG	Work Group
WPAN	Wireless Personal Area Network	YOLO	You Only Look Once
μ -LED	micro-LED		